

The Status and Role of Women in the Pasemah Tribe: Decreasing Acts of Violence Against Women Using Local Wisdom as Value Education

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ABSTRACT: The National Commission on Women in Indonesia, conveyed in its annual report that the number of incidents of violence against women continues to increase from year to year (Kompas, 2016). Sexual violence is one of the most prominent forms of violence, so it is said by some that Indonesia is currently in an emergency condition concerning sexual violence. Some famous cases reported in the media, among others, include the Yuyun junior high school girls in Bengkulu, who were raped and then killed by 14 drunk young men, all the perpetrators were underage; a woman was raped by 19 people and severely traumatized in Manado; and the most recent is the sad case of Eno in Tangerang, who was raped by her boyfriend, who then cruelly pierced a wooden handle into her vagina through to her lungs. Many activists, researchers, educators and other community members have advised including materials for the protection and empowerment of women through formal and in-school education in both families and communities. Most of our societies still regard women and children as weak human beings, who have no right to be protected, and can therefore be used as an outlet for resentment, anger and all forms of negative emotions. Therefore, the education of cultivating the values of tolerance, caring, compassion and respect for women is important and should be a massive movement by various parties to correct this frighteningly incorrect view towards women. It is also suggested that the values education uses the local wisdom evident in the community, because humans learn better from the values that exist in their own environment.

This study was conducted in order to provide information regarding the local knowledge, which the community can use as value education aimed at reducing the acts of violence against women. This study describes the status and roles of women in the Pasemah tribe, South Sumatra. The researcher investigated the values of justice, equality, and respect for women in the tribal culture via the form of daily social interaction and cultural activities. This research used a qualitative method with an ethnography approach. The researcher conducted intensive field research in Pagaralam, South Sumatra, one of the areas where the Pasemah tribe resides. Data collected was in the form of interviews, observations and documents. The techniques used in analyzing the data included a descriptive interpretative method. The data obtained from the research is reported as is, then analyzed and presented descriptively to gain a comprehensive overview of the facts to help answer the questions about the formulation of the problem.

KEYWORDS: Status, Role, Women, Pasemah Tribe, South Sumatra, Indonesia, Violence Against Women